

ACADEMIC INSTITUTION IMPLEMENTATION PROCEDURE ON PUBLIC SECTOR ACCOUNTING ADMINISTRATION IN RIVERS AND BAYELSA STATES

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<p>Keyword: Public sector accounting, Academic institutions, Accounting procedures, Financial reporting, Transparency and accountability</p>	<p>Abstract: <i>The study examined academic institutions implementation procedures on public sector accounting administration in River and Bayelsa States. Three research questions and three null hypotheses guided the study. The study adopted a descriptive research design. The study was carried out in higher institutions of learning in Rivers and Bayelsa State. The population of the study consisted of 413 Bursary staff and there was no sampling due to the manageable size of the population. The entire 413 staff were used as the sample size of the study. A self-structured questionnaire was used for collection for this study. The instrument was subjected to face and content validation by three experts. Cronbach Alpha statistics via SPSS was used to determine the reliability of the instrument and a gran coefficient reliability index of 0.81 was obtained from the clusters. A total of 413 copies of instrument were administered and retrieved by the research and three research assistants. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions and Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was used to test null hypotheses at .05 significance. Based on the analysis the following findings were made; that the current accounting programme adopted by academic institutions in Rivers and Bayelsa State is to high extent, public sector accounting procedures and standard implementation to high extents and public sector accounting administration impacts transparency and accountability to high extent. The following recommendations were made among other academic institution management should review and update their accounting programme regularly, should sustain and strength adherence to accounting standards and ensure regular monitoring, evaluation and compliance checks to maintain consistency and accuracy in financial reporting.</i></p>
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INTRODUCTION

Public sector Accounting refers to the process of recording, classifying, and reporting financial

transaction and event related to governments, and their agencies, (Adams, 2024). According to Adams (2020), public sector accounting may be

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defined as the process of recording, summarizing, analyzing, interpreting and communicating financial statement in aggregate and in details in a public sector organisations. This definition brings us to the established, financed and managed on behalf of the public by the government with public funds. Public sector organization at both the federal and state levels of government include the following: ministries of department, government agencies, boards, commission, councils, government-owned corporations and Government-owned limited liability companies

Public sector Accounting Administration focuses on the management and oversight of public sector accounting systems, including the development and implementation of accounting policies, procedures, and controls. Public Sector Accounting procedures and implementation delve into the practical application of accounting procedures in public sector entities, including the implementation of accounting standards, financial management systems, and internal controls. Implementation according to Hornby (2021), means the putting a decision or plan into effect; execution of Public Sector accounting procedures. Successful Implementation in reliant on valuation standards which ensure that values such as transparency and accountability are uphold, which should be in line with International Best Practices (Abani & Anuolam, 2024). Effective Implementation of Public Sector Accounting Administration can be ensured through: quality of accounting education, accounting curriculum relevance, graduates' employability, public sectors accounting standards compliance, financial reporting

quality, accountability, transparency and public sector financial management effectiveness (Timothy, 2022).

Public Sector Accounting in institutions focuses on the specific accounting needs and challenges of public sector institutions, such as universities, hospitals, and other government-funded organizations, (Abani & Anuolam, 2024). Academic institution refers to universities, polytechnics and colleges that operated accounting system and related programmes. These institutions are also public institution where public sector accounting is adopted in accordance with the public sector Accounting Standard (Nwabueze, 2018). The academic institutions are responsible to provide training and development Programme for accounting practitioners or Administrators, organise workshop, seminars and conferences on public sector accounting practices and standards. It is the duty of the Academic Institutions to ensure implementation of public sector accounting administration in the respective departments (Timothy, 2021)

The accounting and reporting procedures for a government unit differ in some respects, from those of a commercial unit because government and commercial units have different purposes and operation in different environments. The primary purpose of a public unit is to provide services. Also, the freedom of conduct of government units is more limited by legal requirements and regulations. Public sector accounting ought to be based on principles and techniques that promotes economy and efficiency in accounting for public fund, with compliance with applicable legal provisions, (Yinka, 2020).

The accounting system in government accounting, involving the record, summarizing, analyzing, interpreting and communicating of government financial transactions including receipt, custody and disbursement of funds. For government owned corporations, there are acts and laws establishing them. These legislations stipulate sources of revenue, the one aspect being that of government accounting systems are hybrid in nature, one aspect being that of government accounting and being that of commercial accounting they are funded partly by the government they receive recurrent and capital grants they do not make profits and their income statement is usually income and expenditure at the end which increases the accumulated funds (Timothy, 2021).

Statement of the Problem

In Nigeria, there are some lapses in the accounting system; specifically, low compliance to the public sector accounting standards and poor implementation of the procedures in the accounting departments by the practitioners. Nwabueze(2018) identified the lack of standardized procedures to include :inadequate guidelines for implementing public sector accounting programmes in academic institutions and insufficient standardized of accounting practices and procedures.

Other challenges to effective implementation of public sector accounting are: inadequate infrastructure and resources for effective implementation of public sector accounting by educators and practitioners. Further, poor governance and accountability which resulted to weak institutional governance and oversight mechanisms, inadequate accountability and

transparency in public sector accounting practices, Slow adaptation of International Public Sector Accounting Standards (IPSAS) in Rivers and Bayelsa States and limited awareness of understanding of IPSAS among accounting educators and practitioners. (Nwabueze,2018) examined something related to public sector accounting system but not specifically address the puzzle about how academic institutions implement procedures on public sector accounting administration within the scope of the academic institution in Rivers and Bayelsa States. The present study seeks to close this knowledge gap by mounting a scientific investigation that will unravel how the dimensions of academic institutions implement procedures on public sector accounting such as; the current accounting programmes, public sector accounting standards, challenges faced by accounting practitioners and auditing practices interact, within the context of the Academic Institutions in Rivers and Bayelsa States. Hence, the study tends to examine academic institutions implementation procedures on public sector accounting administration in Rivers and Bayelsa States.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of the study was to examine the Academic Institutions Implementation Procedure on Public Sector Accounting Administration in Rivers and Bayelsa States. Specifically, the study sought to:

1. To determine the current accounting programme adopted by Academic Institutions in Rivers and Bayelsa States.
2. To determine public sector accounting procedure and standard implemented by

academic institutions in Rivers and Bayelsa States.

3. To determine how public sector accounting administration in Rivers and Bayelsa States impact transparency and accountability.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What are the current accounting programmes adopted by academic institutions in Rivers and Bayelsa States?

2. What are the public sector accounting procedure and standards implemented by academic institutions in Rivers and Bayelsa States?

3. How do public sector accounting administration impact transparency and accountability in Rivers and Bayelsa States?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance:

1. There is no significant difference in mean ratings of bursary staff of federal and state academic institutions on the current accounting programmes in Rivers and Bayelsa States.

2. There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of bursary staff of federal and state academic institutions on the public sector accounting procedure and standards in Rivers and Bayelsa States.

3. There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of bursary staff of federal and state academic institutions on how public sector accounting administration impacted transparency and accountability in Rivers and Bayelsa States.

METHODOLOGY

This study adopted descriptive survey design, which is described by Mcconbes (2019), as a plan, structure and strategy that an investigator adopts in order to obtain the solution to research problems using questionnaire in collecting, analyzing and interpreting the data. A descriptive survey is that study which aims at collecting data on, and describing in a systematic manner, features or facts about the population (Siedlecki, 2020). The descriptive research design is considered appropriate for this study because it explores and provides a detailed understanding of the characteristics, behavior and conditions of the population under study on how academic institution implementation in public sector accounting procedures and standards in Rivers and Bayelsa State. This study was carried out in Rivers and Bayelsa State. Specifically, in academic institutions of higher learning. Rivers and Bayelsa State are among the six states in South-South Geopolitical Zone of Nigeria. The population of the study consisted of 413 bursary staff from Rivers and Bayelsa state comprising of Ignatius Ajuru University of Education, Captain Elechi Amadi Polytechnics Rumuola, Port Hacourt, Ken Sarowiwa Polytechnics Bori, University of Port Harcourt, Federal College of Education (Technical) Omoku, Federal University Otuoke and Niger Delta University Amasoma. There was no sampling, because the entire population was used for this study, which is census sampling method was adopted.

The instrument for data collection was a self-structured questionnaire with a 5-point rating scale of: Very High Extent (VHE-5points), High Extent (HE-4points), Moderate Extent (ME-

3points), Low Extent (LE-2points) and Very Low Extent (VLE-1points). The research instrument way subjected to face and content validation by three experts. Two from the Department of Business Education and one from Measurement and Evaluation of Faculty all of Education, Rivers and Bayelsa State University. Their inputs and corrections in terms of clarity and appropriate of items in addressing the variable of the study were used by the researcher and corrections to be effected to get the final draft of the instrument of the study. To establish the reliability of the instrument, test-retest method and Cronbach Alpha, via Statistical Packages for Social Science (SPSS) was used to determine the reliability coefficient of the instrument, 20 copies of the questionnaire were distributed to the bursary staff in Imo State University Owerri, which is not part of the study area. Reliability coefficient of the clusters are: 0.82, 0.85, 0.79, 0.80 and 0.77. The grand coefficient reliability index of 0.81, was deemed highly reliable for the study. The researcher administered the instrument with the

help of the three research assistants who were briefed and guided on how to administer and retrieve the questionnaire from the respondents accordingly. Out of 413 questionnaire distributed, 306 were returned and used for data analysis. The research used mean and standard deviation to answer the research questions while Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was used to test null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The decision rule was based on the mean score of 3.00 and above was the benchmark for High Extent (HE), while any item with a mean score below 3.00 was considered low extent. If the calculated f-value is less than the f-table value the null hypotheses was not rejected and if calculated f-ratio is greater than the f-table value, the null hypothesis was rejected.

Analysis of Data and Results/Hypotheses

The data are presented in the following table below:

Research Question 1: What are the current accounting programmes adopted by academic institutions in Rivers and Bayelsa States?

Table 1: Computed Means and Standard Deviations Scores of Respondents on the current accounting programmes adopted by academic institutions in Rivers and Bayelsa States.

S/N	Statements	Bayelsa = 28	SD	Rivers = 278	SD	Remark	
		\bar{x}	Sd ₁	Rmks	Sd ₂		
1	Academic institution curriculum includes Public Sector Accounting	3.49	.685	HE	3.22	0.95	High Extent

2	Academic institutions adopt International Accounting Standards in their accounting system	3.53	.912	HE	3.59	0.58	High Extent
3	Academic institutions Programme meets the need of Industry.	3.64	.541	HE	3.02	0.90	High Extent
4	Academic Institutions ensure that their accounting programme meet regulatory requirements.	3.53	.787	HE	3.27	1.08	High Extent
5	Academic Institution reviews and update their accounting programme regulatory	3.61	.520	High extent	3.49	1.11	High Extent
	Grand Mean/Std Dev.=	3.56	0.69	High extent	3.32	0.69	High Extent

Source: Researcher’s Field Survey (2025)

The result in table 4.1 shows the current accounting programmes adopted by academic institutions with the grand mean of 3.56 and 3.32 which signifies High extent for Bayelsa and Rivers respectively. The five items indicate to a high extent that Academic institution curriculum includes Public Sector Accounting, International

Accounting Standards and that academic institutions meets the need of Industry.

Research Question 2:

What are the public sector accounting procedure and standards implemented by academic institutions in Rivers and Bayelsa States?

Table 2: Computed Means and Standard Deviations Scores of Respondents on the public sector accounting procedure and standards implemented by academic institutions in Rivers and Bayelsa States.

S/N	Statements	Bayelsa = 28			Rivers = 278		
		Mean \bar{x}	Standard Deviation Sd ₁	Remarks	Mean \bar{x}	Standard Deviation Sd ₂	Remarks
1	Academic Institutions ensure compliance with	3.68	.685	High extent	3.64	.541	High extent

	public sector accounting standards in their financial reporting.						
2	Public sector procedures are strictly adhered to by academic Institutions	3.37	.639	High extent	3.59	.829	High extent
3	Academic Institutions adopt generally accepted accounting principles.	3.65	.562	High extent	3.56	.645	High extent
4	Nigerian public accounting standards are adopted by academic Institutions.	3.49	.501	High extent	3.78	.639	High extent
5	Academic institutions implement accrual-based accounting in their public sector accounting procedures.	3.90	.387	High extent	3.61	.514	High extent
	Grand Mean / S.D	3.62	0.55	High extent	3.64	0.64	High extent

Source: Researcher’s Field Survey (2025)

Data contained in table 1.2 shows that public sector accounting procedure and standards are implemented by academic institutions in Rivers

and Bayelsa States with the grand mean scores of 3.62 and 3.64 respectively. The five items indicate to a high extent that Academic Institutions ensure

compliance with public sector accounting standards in their financial reporting, Public sector procedures are strictly adhered to and implement accrual-based accounting in their public sector accounting procedures.

Research Question 3: How do public sector accounting administration impact transparency and accountability in Rivers and Bayelsa States?

Table 3: Computed Means and Standard Deviations Scores of Respondents on the extent to which public sector accounting administration impact transparency and accountability in Rivers and Bayelsa States.

S/N	Statements	Bayelsa = 28			Rivers = 278		
		Mean \bar{X}	Standard Deviation Sd ₁	Remarks	Mean \bar{X}	Standard Deviation Sd ₂	Remarks
1	Public sector accounting administration promote transparency in financial reporting in Rivers and Balyasa states.	3.61	.720	High extent	3.97	.547	High extent
2	International public sector accounting standard impact accountability in academics institution in Rivers and Bayesa states.	3.65	.654	High extent	3.38	.661	High extent
3	Public sector accounting administrator provide timely and accurate	3.36	.492	High extent	3.88	.704	High extent

	financial information to stake holders.						
4	Public sector accounting administration ensures effectiveness financial records and reporting.	3.62	.647	High extent	3.50	.694	High extent
5	Effective public sector accounting administration check on the level of corruption in Rivers and Bayesa states.	3.37	.578	High extent	3.55	.918	High extent
	Grand Mean / S.D	3.52	0.62	High extent	3.66	0.70	High extent

Researcher’s Field Survey (2025)

The result in table 4.3 shows that Public sector accounting administration promote transparency in financial reporting, Public sector accounting administrator provide timely and accurate financial information to stake holders in Rivers and Balyelsa states to a high extent with the grand mean and standard deviation of 3.62 and 3.66. The five items indicate to a high extent that public sector accounting administration impact transparency and accountability in Rivers and Bayelsa States with the grand mean and standard deviation of 3.62 and 3.66.

Testing of Hypotheses

Hypotheses were tested using ANOVA statistics and the results are presented in the tables that follows: Example of details of F-ratio computation is given in Appendix D.

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant difference in mean ratings of bursary staff of federal and state academic institutions on the current accounting programmes in Rivers and Bayelsa States.

Table 4: ANOVA on the Mean Ratings of Bursary Staff of Federal and State Academic Institutions on the Current Accounting Programmes in Rivers and Bayelsa States

Sources of Variance	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	α	F-cal	F-crit
Between Groups	6.595	7	.942	0.05	9.286	4.15
Within Groups	30.233	298	.101			
Total	36.828	305				

Source: Researcher’s Field Survey (2025)

From table 4.6, the F-calculated value of 9.29 is greater than the F-critical table value of 4.15 at 0.05% level of significance and degree of freedom of 1 and 306. While the sum of squares (SS) for between groups was 6.60 and the (mean sum of squares (MS) 0.94, for within groups (Error Variance), it was 30.23 and 0.10 respectively. Thus, the null hypothesis of no significant difference in the mean ratings of bursary staff of federal and state academic institutions on the current accounting programmes in Rivers and

Bayelsa States was rejected meaning there is significant difference in the mean ratings of bursary staff of federal and state academic institutions on the current accounting programmes in Rivers and Bayelsa States.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of bursary staff of federal and state academic institutions on the public sector accounting procedure and standards in Rivers and Bayelsa States.

Table 5: ANOVA on the Mean Ratings of Bursary Staff of Federal and State Academic Institutions on the Public Sector Accounting Procedure and Standards in Rivers and Bayelsa States

Sources of Variance	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	α	F	F-crit
Between Groups	15.468	7	2.210	0.05	15.634	4.15
Within Groups	42.119	298	.141			
Total	57.587	305				

Source: Researcher’s Field Survey (2025)

From table 4.7, the F-calculated value of 15.63 is greater than the F-critical table value of 4.15 at 0.05% level of significance and degree of freedom of 1 and 306. While the sum of squares (SS) for between groups was 15.47 and the (mean sum of squares (MS) 2.21, for within groups (Error Variance), it was 57.59 and 0.14 respectively.

Thus, the null hypothesis of no significant difference in the mean ratings of bursary staff of federal and state academic institutions on the public sector accounting procedure and standards in Rivers and Bayelsa States was rejected meaning there is significant difference in the mean ratings of bursary staff of federal and

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state academic institutions on the public sector accounting procedure and standards in Rivers and Bayelsa States.

Hypothesis 3: There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of bursary staff of federal and

Table 6: ANOVA on the Mean Ratings of Bursary Staff of Federal and State Academic Institutions on how Public Sector Accounting Administration Impacted Transparency and Accountability in Rivers and Bayelsa States

Sources of Variance	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	α	F	F-crit
Between Groups	6.028	7	.861	0.05	11.79	4.15
Within Groups	21.776	298	.073			
Total	27.805	306				

Source: Researcher’s Field Survey (2025)

From table 4.8, the F-calculated value of 11.79 is greater than the F-critical table value of 4.15 at 0.05% level of significance and degree of freedom of 1 and 306. While the sum of squares (SS) for between groups was 6.028 and the (mean sum of squares (MS) 0.86, for within groups (Error Variance), it was 21.78 and 0.73 respectively. Thus, the null hypothesis of no significant difference in the mean ratings of bursary staff of federal and state academic institutions on the public sector accounting procedure and standards in Rivers and Bayelsa States was rejected meaning there is significant difference in the mean ratings of bursary staff of federal and state academic institutions on the public sector accounting procedure and standards in Rivers and Bayelsa States.

Discussion of Findings

Findings from research question one with regard to the extent to which current accounting programmes are adopted by academic institutions in Rivers and Bayelsa States revealed

state academic institutions on how public sector accounting administration impacted transparency and accountability in Rivers and Bayelsa States.

that, from the qualitative and quantitative data analyzed, the adoption of current accounting programmes is to a high extent. This finding is in agreement with the view of Chaudhary (2017), who opined that effective accounting programmes enhance both teaching and administrative efficiency as they create a professional learning environment and promote collaborative educational management. In agreement with Chaudhary’s view, Fernández, Fernández, and Aburto (2019) observed that the adoption of modern accounting programmes and standards helps administrators and accounting educators to gain more professional experience while providing accurate financial information for decision-making in educational management. The researcher is of the view that academic institutions in Rivers and Bayelsa states ought to continuously update and implement current accounting programmes that meet international standards, promote accountability, and ensure financial transparency. Also, accounting

programmes ought to blend theoretical knowledge with practical applications that strengthen institutional governance and improve the quality of financial management across tertiary institutions. Similarly, the corresponding hypothesis revealed that there is a significant difference in the mean ratings of accounting educators in federal and State academic institutions on the extent to which current accounting programmes are adopted for effective financial administration and accountability

Findings from research question two with regard to the level to which public sector accounting procedures and standards are implemented by academic institutions in Rivers and Bayelsa States revealed that, from the qualitative and quantitative data analyzed, public sector accounting procedures and standards are implemented to a high extent. This finding is in agreement with the view of Svart (2018), who depicts that public sector accounting procedures provide a structured framework for recording, reporting, and managing financial transactions in government-funded institutions, ensuring accountability and transparency. In agreement with this views of Svart, Ojala (2019) opined that the consistent implementation of public sector accounting standards helps academic institutions maintain uniformity in financial reporting and enables effective monitoring of public funds.

The researcher is of the view that academic institutions in Rivers and Bayelsa States should continue to strengthen the implementation of public sector accounting procedures and standards by ensuring compliance with government financial regulations, providing periodic training for accounting staff, and

integrating digital financial management tools to enhance efficiency and accountability. Similarly, the corresponding hypothesis showed that there is significant difference in the mean ratings of accounting educators in federal and State academic institutions on the level to which public sector accounting procedures and standards are implemented for effective financial management and accountability.

Findings from research question three with regard to the extent to which public sector accounting administration impacts transparency and accountability in Rivers and Bayelsa States revealed that, from the qualitative and quantitative data analyzed, public sector accounting administration has a high impact on transparency and accountability.

This finding is in disagreement with the view of Ali (2023) depicts that many public organizations still face challenges in achieving transparency due to weak accounting systems and inconsistent application of financial policies. According to Ali et al., the lack of standardized accounting practices often leads to poor accountability and mismanagement of resources within government institutions. In agreement with this views Ali, Tarun (2023) depicts that effective public sector accounting administration enhances transparency by ensuring that financial data are accurately recorded, stored, and reported in a systematic manner. He explained that when accounting records, such as budgetary allocations, expenditures, and audit reports are properly maintained and made accessible, stakeholders can verify institutional performance and detect irregularities promptly.

Improve internal control mechanisms, and build public trust in the management of public funds.

The researcher is of the view that effective public sector accounting administration eliminates the possibility of financial misrepresentation by promoting integrity, openness, and accountability in financial reporting. It allows academic institutions to maintain accurate records, verify transactions, and ensure that all stakeholders including staff, students, and the public have confidence in the management of institutional finances. Similarly, the corresponding hypothesis showed that there is significant difference in the mean ratings of accounting educators in federal and State academic institutions on the extent to which public sector accounting administration impacts transparency and accountability in academic institutions

Conclusion

This study examined the implementation procedures adopted by academic institutions in the administration of public sector accounting, with a focus on evaluating their effectiveness, challenges, and implications for transparency and accountability. The findings revealed that the implementation of public sector accounting procedures in academic institutions plays a crucial role in ensuring prudent financial management, proper record-keeping, and compliance with statutory regulations. It also showed that when appropriate procedures are followed, institutional resources are better utilized, and the objectives of accountability and efficiency are achieved.

However, the study identified certain constraints such as inadequate training of accounting

personnel, insufficient technological infrastructure, poor monitoring mechanisms, and limited adherence to standardized accounting practices. These challenges undermine the effective implementation of public sector accounting principles in academic settings.

Based on the analysis, it can be concluded that the successful administration of public sector accounting in academic institutions depends largely on strict adherence to established procedures, capacity building for accounting staff, and the integration of modern accounting technologies. Strengthening institutional frameworks, promoting transparency, and enforcing compliance will not only enhance financial accountability but also contribute to the overall performance and sustainability of academic institutions.

Educational Implication

The findings of this study have several important educational implications for academic institutions, policymakers, educators, and students. The implementation of public sector accounting procedures within academic institutions provides a framework for promoting accountability, transparency, and effective management of educational finances. This, in turn, has direct and indirect impacts on the teaching, learning, and administrative processes within the education sector.

The proper implementation of public sector accounting procedures ensures that funds allocated to academic institutions are judiciously utilized for educational development. When financial records are properly managed and reported, it leads to better budgeting, resource allocation, and the provision of quality

educational facilities, thereby improving the overall learning environment for students.

Integrating public sector accounting principles into the curriculum of business and accounting education helps students develop the necessary competencies and ethical standards required for managing public funds. It enhances their understanding of financial accountability and prepares them for careers in public administration, finance, and education management.

The study emphasizes the need for continuous professional development and training of accounting personnel and educators in academic institutions. This will enable them to effectively apply modern accounting systems and comply with public sector financial regulations. Such capacity building strengthens institutional governance and promotes the credibility of academic administration. The effective implementation of public sector accounting procedures encourages transparency in academic management, reduces financial misappropriation, and fosters trust among

REFERENCES

Abani, M.O. & Anuolam, M.O (2024). The effect of International Public Sector Accounting Standards on Transparency, Accountability and Good Governance in Government Ministries, Nigeria. *Journal of Research in Business and Management* 12(11), 13-20.

Adams, R.A. (2024). Public sector Accounting and Finance made simple. Corporate Publisher Ventures.

stakeholders. When accountability becomes an integral part of educational administration, it cultivates a culture of integrity and responsibility among both staff and students.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study the following recommendations were made:

1. It is recommended that academic institutions should continuously review and update their accounting programmes to align with current trends, international standards, and technological advancements in public sector accounting.
2. It is recommended that institutions should sustain and strengthen adherence to these standards by ensuring regular monitoring, evaluation, and compliance checks to maintain consistency and accuracy in financial reporting.
3. It is recommended that management of academic institutions should institutionalize periodic public financial disclosures and promote open communication to further enhance public trust and institutional credibility.

Eke and Amesi (2024), Adoption of International Public Sector Account Standard and Financial Reporting Quality in Universities in Rivers and Bayelsa States.

Eke, O. (2023). Fiscal Responsibility Act and budget implementation in Nigerian Public Institutions: A case study of Rivers and Bayelsa States. *Public Finance Quarterly*, 12(3),

Emenike, C. (2023). Challenges in public sector accounting implementation: Policy and

institutional perspectives. *Nigerian Journal of Accounting Research*, 15(1), 88–102.

Henry, A. (2023). Digital auditing and financial integrity in public institutions. *Journal of Emerging Accounting Practices*, 9(3), 41–59.

Nwabueze, P.B.C (2022). *Element of Public Sector Accounting*. Spring Time Press.

Nwankwo, A. C. (2020). Enhancing employability through practical experience in accounting education. *Journal of Accounting Education*, 35(2), 45-60.

Timothy, C.N. (2021). *Introduction to Public Sector Accounting*. Great stars Publishers International Company.

Yinka, MA. Muyiwa, E.D, Victor, O.O &Yemi, A. O (2024). Implementation of International Public Sector Accounting Standards on the Financial Reporting Quality in the Nigerian Public Sector. *Fuoye Journal of Accounting and Management*. 7(1), 1-16.